

Feng Shenyu stele (505 CE)
Feng Shenyu deng erbainian ren zaoxiang bei
馮神育等二百廿人造像碑

RODO PFISTER 2021, Casual Notes for Friends 2.
Research Institute for the History of Afroeurasian Life Sciences •
Basel, Switzerland

OVERVIEW 1
FENG SHENYU STELE TEXT TRANSCRIPT 1
STUDIES 2
SCHWARTZ CUT, DETAIL OF FRONT SIDE, NOVEMBER 30, 1987 8
RUBBINGS 10
CBETA FENG SHENYU STELE TEXT TRANSCRIPT 15

Overview

“Daoist practitioner Feng Shenyu and some 200 other community members Daoist stele”
Daomin Feng Shenyu tongyi erbai ren deng dao zaoxiang bei 道民馮神育同邑二百人等道造像碑
Date: 8 November 505 CE 正始二年九月二十六日 (cf. ZHANG Xunliao 2010: 447, Table 1)
Daoist public stele: 150 cm high, 66-70 cm wide, and 35 cm thick.

Dating acc. 北朝佛教石刻拓片百品索引:

No.	王朝	年号	西曆	名称	頁	題跋
11.	北魏	正始 2 年(505)	505 CE	馮神育等二百廿人造像碑	26	--

http://www.isc.meiji.ac.jp/~ishiken/_userdata/list-hokubutu.pdf

Feng Shenyu stele text transcript

【經文資訊】北朝佛教石刻拓片百品第 01 冊 No. 0011 馮神育等二百廿人造像碑

【版本記錄】CBETA 電子佛典 2016.06, 完成日期: 2016/06/15

http://tripitaka.cbeta.org/mobile/index.php?index=I01n0011_001

textbook *en chinois* http://archive.cbeta.org/download/download.php?file=pdf_a4/I/I0011.pdf

北朝佛教石刻拓片百品 第 01 冊

No. 11 馮神育等二百廿人造像碑 (1 卷)

【顏娟英主編】第 1 卷, 2016

Note: Character variant written for yì 邑 throughout stele text.

Studies

ZHAO Kangmin 趙康民 [Lintong xian bowuguan 臨潼縣博物館]

°1985 [pdf]

Shaanxi Lintong de Beichao zaoxiangbei 山西臨潼的北朝造像碑,
in: wenwu 文物 4: 15-26, 19 figs., 100 (pl. 3).

[Feng Shenyu stele (正始二年造像碑): 16+20, figs. 1-5 (see *Rubbings* below).]

Fig. 1: 正始二年造像碑

KAMIZUKA Yoshiko 神塚淑子

1993

Nanbokuchō jidai no dōkyō zōzō 南北朝時代の道教造像 – *shūkyō shisō-shi-teki kōsatsu o chūshin ni* 宗教思想史的考察を中心に,

in: TONAMI Mamoru 礪波護 (ed. *hen* 編) 1993: *Chūgokuchūsei no*

bunbutsu 中國中時の文物. [Chinese Medieval Civilization] Kyōto: Kyōto

daigaku jinbun kagaku kenkyūjo 京都大学人文科学研究所,

pp. 225-289.

[230: Feng Shenyu stele.]

SHAANXI SHENG KAOGU YANJIU SUO 陝西省考古研究所, SHAANXI SHENG YAOXIAN YAO-

WANGSHAN BOWUGUAN 陝西省耀縣藥王山博物館, SHAANXI LINTONG SHI BOWUGUAN

山西臨潼市博物館, BEIJING LIAO JIN CHENGYUAN BOWUGUAN 北京遼金城垣博物館 (eds.)

1996

Beichao fodayao zaoxiangbei jingxuan 北朝佛道造像碑精選.

Tianjin: Tianjin guji chubanshe 天津古籍出版社.

[50-57: Feng Shenyu stele.]

ABE Stanley K.

*°1996-1997 [pdf]

Heterological Visions: Northern Wei Daoist Sculpture from Shaanxi Province,
in: Cahiers d'Extrême-Asie 9 (1996-1997): 69-83, 10 figs.

(Mémorial Anna Seidel: Religions traditionnelles d'Asie orientale,

Tome II) <<https://www.jstor.org/stable/45276185>>

<<https://doi.org/10.3406/asie.1996.1111>> (without fig. 1)

[Résumé: L'étude de Stanley Abe traite de plusieurs exemplaires de stèles taoïstes du Yaowangshan (Nord Shaanxi) remontant aux Wei du Nord. Ces œuvres illustrent plusieurs modèles différents d'art visuel taoïste et leurs relations étroites avec l'iconographie de l'art bouddhique de cette époque. Certaines œuvres semblent refléter une volonté consciente de ranger côte à côte figures bouddhiques et taoïstes. Suivant la suggestion de Bokenkamp dans son article ici-même, les œuvres sont examinées à la lumière de connexions possibles avec des textes Lingbao et avec la stratégie Lingbao visant à s'appropriier les concepts et le langage bouddhiques. Na-

guère, Anna Seidel avait suggéré que deux autres petites sculptures taoïstes, du début du VI^e siècle, pourraient représenter sur la gauche et sur la droite les Parfaits de la tradition Lingbao. La publication récente des stèles taoïstes du Shaanxi étudiées ici semble confirmer ses vues.]

Fig. 9 Feng Shenyu stele, front, dated to 505, Lintong Museum. Photo by the author.

Fig. 10 Feng Shenyu stele, rear, dated to 505, Lintong Museum. Photo by the author.

79-80: “One other stele (Figure 9), from the area of Lintong, south of Yaowangshan and not far from Xian, provides us with still another perspective. The large stele dated to 505, the earliest from the site, was the donation of a Daomin Feng Shenyu 道民馮神育 and others.³⁷ The principle image here is a badly damaged seated figure in meditative pose, right hand in *abhaya mudrā*, dressed in monastic robes and flanked by two standing attendants. Below the single niche is an incense burner in the form of a *boshanlu* with two supplicants dressed in the coats and pants favored by non-Han Chinese people. The lower section is covered with orderly rows of similarly dressed male donor figures, each with an identifying colophon. The rear face (Figure 10) features a single figure in dress and posture almost identical with the image on the front. The right hand, however, holds a fan, an indication that it is a Daoist deity. Below are neat rows of female donors depicted in non-Han dress also with identifying colophons. The left side has one niche at the top containing a single meditating figure in monk’s robes.³⁸ Below is the dedicatory inscription flanked by male donors. The right side has at the top a single seated Daoist figure dressed in a belted robe with both hands placed straight down in front of its crossed ankles. If the principle image on the front face image and the left side figure are taken as Buddhist, these would form a symmetrical group with the two Daoist images on the rear and right side.³⁹ At the same time, the patrons of the work identify themselves through a similarly parallel use of Buddhist and Daoist forms. The identifying colophons of some of the female and all of the male donors begin with *yizi* 邑子, an appellation often encountered in Buddhist donations by lay religious associations known as *yiyi* 邑義 or *heyi* 合邑. In fact, one part of the inscription describes the donors of the image as a *heyi* of 220 people. Consistent with Buddhist donations, a few colophons on the left side identify the leaders of the association as *yishi* 邑士; on the opposite side next to the image of the Daoist deity, we find two individuals identified as the Daoist equivalent, *daoshi* 道士. And in the dedication, the lead donor, Feng Shenyu has the title of *daomin*. / All of the above suggests a conscious hybrid approach towards this donation by a large association. One wonders, however, who is appropriating what in such a work? Is this another example of the Lingbao-inspired appropriation of Buddhist forms, in this case the Buddhist *heyi* organized for a Daoist donation? Or did a *heyi* of lay Buddhists convert to Lingbao en masse? Could the careful balance of Daoist and Buddhist elements indicate a choice on the part of the donor group to express their belief in both Daoist and Buddhist teachings? Finally, is it possible that the Feng Shenyu stele represents a counter-attack on the part of lay Buddhists who, faced with works such as the Yao Boduo stele, retaliated against *huahu* theory through a work which represented Daoist deities as nothing more than forms of Buddhist ones? /

37 Dated 正始二年九月二十六日; 154 cm. in height. See Kamizuka, “Nanbokuchō jidai no dōkyō zōzō,” 230; as 正始二年遺像碑 in Lintong Xian Bowuguan 臨潼縣博物館 “Shaanxi Lintong 山西臨潼,” 15-20.

38 Rubbings of all four sides are reproduced in Lintong Xian Bowuguan, “Shaanxi Lintong,” figs. 2-5.

39 The Lintong Xian Bowuguan publication (see note 37) lists all of the icons on the stele as Buddhist.”

*2001 [pdf]

Provenance, Patronage, and Desire: Northern Wei Sculpture from Shaanxi Province,

in: *Ars Orientalis* 31 (2001): 1-30, 34 figs.

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/4629578>

<https://archive.org/details/arsorientalar312001univ/>

[Abstract: Northern Wei sculpture from Shaanxi province was produced for a variety of functions and religious purposes by patrons organized in different forms and representing a range of social classes. While past studies of Northern Wei sculpture have often been guided by a spatial model that is oriented along a metropolitan/provincial divide, this essay proposes an alternative approach which assumes that differences of provenance are modulated by the function of the work, the social class and political position of the patrons, the organizational form of the patronage, as well as religious and political motivations. Finally, the training and assumptions that scholars bring to their studies guide what kinds of questions may be (and may not be) asked in our work, and these in turn structure and limit the type of conclusions that may be drawn. Ultimately, an awareness of our own historical and subjective relation to the materials we study offers us the possibility of understanding why we choose to pursue certain lines of research to the exclusion of others. –

15-17, figs. 24-25 (front and rear rubbing): *The Feng Shenyu Stele.*]

FIG. 1.
Shaanxi province map (by Linda Huff).

*2002

Ordinary Images.

Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

[408p., 230 halftones, 5 maps, 20 line drawings. ISBN: 9780226000442.]

[Description: This richly illustrated book explores the large body of sculpture, paintings, and other religious imagery produced for China's common classes from the third to the sixth centuries C.E. In contrast to the works made for imperial patrons, illustrious monastics, or other luminaries, these ordinary images—modest in scale, mass produced, and at times incomplete—were created for those of lesser standing. Because they cannot be related to well-known historical figures or social groups, these images have been considered a largely nebulous, undistinguished mass of works.

Situating his study in the gaps between conventional categories such as Buddhism, Daoism, and Chinese popular art, Abe examines works—including some of the earliest known examples of Buddha-like images in China—that were commissioned by patrons of modest standing and produced by nameless artists and artisans. Sophisticated and lucidly written, *Ordinary Images*

offers an unprecedented exploration of the lively and diverse nature of image making and popular practices. –

Contents: List of Maps / List of Illustrations / Acknowledgments / Conventions

One. Ordinary Images

Two. Small Beginnings

Three. Local Context

Four. Sinicization

Five. Alternatives

Conclusion. Ordinary Practice

Notes / Bibliography / Index. –

274-281: Feng Shenyu stele.]

ZHANG Zexun 張澤珣

2009

Bei Wei guanzhong daojiao zaoxiangji yanjiu 北魏關中道教造像記研究.

Macau: Universidade de Macau. [270p.; ISBN: 978-99937-94-37-0.]

[Description: 本書記錄了北魏時期奉道者的身份、造像奉為及造像發願目的，也記錄了當時宗教儀式活動的部分，同時造像碑的圖像也展示了部分儀式活動的內容。在道教倡導男女民立壇宇禮拜供養的文化風尚影響下，民眾組織了叫作邑、合邑的宗教社群或以家為宗教社群形式的造像活動。信士們透過造像供養與道教齋的儀式修行之法結合，形成一種新的禮儀文化。

透過造像題名，顯示北魏道教信仰社群一方面繼承了傳統裡、社的組織形式，另一方面，直接繼承了天師道的教戒和齋官制度，在對雙教碑的造像記考察，道教作為北魏地方民眾信仰的主流文化，道教沒有排斥佛教，而是包容和影響了佛教，在社會中發揮著重要的作用。 –

151-154: Feng Shenyu stele.]

ZHANG Xunliao 張勳燎

°2010 [pdf]

Daoist Stelae of the Northern Dynasties,

in: LAGERWEY John & LÜ Pengzhi (eds.) °2010 *Early Chinese Religion, Part Two: The Period of Division (220-589 AD)*. (Handbook of Oriental Studies, section four, China, volume 21-2) Leiden, Boston: Brill, pp. 437-543, 8 figs., 4 tables.

<<https://doi.org/10.1163/ej.9789004175853.i-1564.65>>

[• Table 1: Northern Dynasties Daoist stelae: 446-

• Feng Shenyu stele: 439 n. 3, 447, 458, 488-490, 496, 500 (title *daoshi* 道士), 502, 507, 508, 509, 513f., no figs.

488-490: “*Public stelae* / On the whole, communal stelae appear a couple of decades after household stelae. According to the extant examples, there are at least two kinds of communal stelae that appear in the Northern Dynasties. The first of these is the public stele. The Feng Shenyu stele (505) is to date the earliest example of public stele. This stele is 150 cm high, 66–70 cm wide, and 35 cm thick. The dedicatory inscription on the left side of the stele indicates that the adherents of this community identified themselves as “Daoist practitioners.” These words are supported by the iconography on the other three sides of the stele. While the heads of the deities on the obverse and reverse niches are completely missing, they are clearly holding tablets. The main deities carved in the reverse niches hold sambar-tail chowries, and the deities on the right side are donned with crowns with cross-shaped pins. The above inscription also mentions that “the over 200 people of the same community as Daoist practitioner Feng Shenyu . . . erect this stone image” and “the 220 people of this community carve a stone statue in this place.” Such statements clearly reveal the sentiments often contained in communal stelae and give clues to the number of people participating in such associations. The inscription is replete with names of adherents attached to titles of various sorts; their positions cover the gamut of those mentioned throughout public stelae. Thus the Feng Shenyu stele is perhaps the best representative for those stelae erected by such diverse Daoist communities. Of the names that are visible on the stele we see the following titles (number of adherents listed for each title in brackets): Daoist practitioner [6], master of pure faith (*qingxin shi* 清信士) [1], register pupil (*lusheng* 錄生) [17], Daoist master [7], ritual master of the three caverns (*sandong fashi* 三洞法師) [4], family master (*menshi* 門師) [1],⁹⁷ community master (*yishi* 邑師) [1],⁹⁸ keeper of registers (*dianlu* 典錄) [2], attendant [2], community chief (*yizheng* 邑正) [3], community elder [1], “female master [. . .]” [1], community members [76], monastery controller (*weina* 唯那) [1], site donor and altar director (*shidi* [. . .] *tan* [*zhu*] 施地□檀[主]) [1], and people without a title [55].⁹⁹ No one among all these adherents is listed as a main donor, but this position is most likely held by “Daoist practitioner Feng Shenyu” and others. To the right of the niche on the obverse is a title that

reads “[images] constructed by Fu Yongle 傅永樂, ritual master of the three caverns from Niyang 泥陽 of Pingding 平定”; this indicates that Fu Yongle, a high-level Daoist priest, was responsible for the design of this stele, and his name was carved at the end of the construction process. While the names and titles to the left and right of the carved niches on all four sides are not accompanied by images, those below the niches do have images of the adherents. This gives the impression that there was not enough room for images of all the adherents, so the makers of this stele crammed their names into the space on the sides. There are people with 25 different surnames in this community—Yang 楊, Wang 王, Li 李, Feng 馮—but Feng is the most prominent and must have been one of the leading families in the area. There are no women on the obverse or the two sides of the stele, and the women included are concentrated below the niche on the reverse. ~~Aside from the monastery controller Feng Daoqin 馮道欽 on the left side of the reverse, there are no explicitly Buddhist elements on this stele.~~ Since the Feng Shenyu stele does not contain Buddhist characteristics, it is a representative example of a pure Daoist stele. / 97 The family master on this stele is Zhang Mingyu 張明玉, who is located to the right of the thurifer beneath the Daoist deity on the obverse.

98 The community master, Feng Hongbiao 馮洪標, is located to the left of the thurifer beneath the Daoist deity on the obverse.

99 There are 57 womens’ names listed below the niche on the reverse, and only two, Yang Fengji 楊鳳姬 and Wang Qing[. . .] 王清□ are identified as community members.”

509: “Third, there are many women featured in communal stelae, but there are relatively few who are given full status in the group with the title community member. To the left and right of the reverse niche of Feng Shenyu stele (505), for instance, we see a keeper of registers, a Daoist master, a Daoist practitioner, an attendant, a community chief, and others totaling 20 people. Aside from the female master, Wang Asao 王阿嫂 (who is featured in the very bottom, right corner of this group of esteemed members), there are no women carved among this group. There is, however, a group of 57 adherents that is inscribed under Mother Wang in the right corner with features that appear and names that sound distinctly feminine.¹⁶² It is apparent that the creators of this monument determined that the women should be kept in a separate section.¹⁶³ And although there are almost 60 women on this stele, only the community members Yang Fengji 楊鳳姬 and Wang Qing[. . .] 王清□ carved into the top row have a title other than a surname and personal name. It is possible that Mother Wang Asao is the mother of one of the community masters or Daoist masters and is therefore in a position to be placed among the high-ranking males surrounding the niche. Given the group of females placed beneath her, Wang likely led the group of females associated with this community. This example also shows that while it was not impossible for women to be ranked with an official title of a community, it was a rather rare occasion for women to be held in such esteem. /

162 Examples of these women’s names include Li Anji 李安姬, Feng Weiji 馮魏姬, Zhang Baifeng 張白鳳, Yang Leji 楊樂姬, Yuan Chounü 袁醜女, Yang Maoji 楊毛姬, Wang Hongji 王洪姬, Yin Chounü 尹醜女, Zhang Wumei 張武媚, Guo Shennü 郭神女, Li Gongzhu 李公主, Zhao Qingnü 趙青女, Bai Beiji 柏北姬.

163 *Beichao Fo Dao*, pp. 51 and 128.”

513-514: “After a stele was officially completed, this monument also served as a locus for community ritual whereby adepts would gather around the stele during fasts. This ritual activity is supported by a variety of titles on stele inscriptions that feature words like “fast” and “altar” (*tan* 壇). The writer of the writ of commitments in the Feng Shenyu stele (505) states that “220 people of this community come together to erect a stone statue,” and elsewhere says that “the Daoist practitioner Feng Shenyu and the 200-odd people of this community submit themselves at the altar and seek the fruits of the other world by carving this stone image.” The titles that suggest such activity include: fast director,¹⁷² grand fast director,¹⁷³ fast supervisor,¹⁷⁴ director of the altar image,¹⁷⁵ altar director,¹⁷⁶ altar guard,¹⁷⁷ director of the altar guard,¹⁷⁸ and director of the altar day.¹⁷⁹ The “fast” in these titles refers to a periodic purification held by the Daoist community, and “altar” refers to the space where offerings are made at such ceremonies. The altar, usually called a mystic altar (*xuantan* 玄壇), plays a central role in the experience of a Daoist fast. In the Feng Shenyu stele (505), for example, we see some further evidence of how site donor Feng Daodu helps prepare the permanent ritual space of the stele site by conducting a series of fasts and offerings on its grounds. Texts, like the Regulations for the practice of Daoism, speak of how one should use brick, stone, and mud to construct an altar in front of a hall containing an image of the Celestial Worthy, and how one should use wood to make an altar with three, five, or twelve tiers.¹⁸⁰ For those aforementioned stelae that were placed outdoors, we assume that there might have been an altar area of mud or stone, but it is unlikely that these adherents constructed a wood altar. /

172 Cai Hong stele (548) includes a “fast director Cai Jixing 蔡寄興.” See *Daojia jinshi lue*, p. 33.

173 Cai Hong stele (548) contains a “grand fast director Cai Fengren 蔡鳳仁.” See *Daojia jinshi lue*, p. 33.

174 Beneath the reverse niche of the Pang Shuang stele (527) is a person labeled “fast supervisor Pang Shenxi 龐神熏.” See *Beichao Fo Dao*, p. 136.

- 175 The Guo Faluo stele (526) includes a “director of the altar image Zhang Ao 張教.”
 176 See the Cai Hong stele (548) and the Xin Yanzhi stele (548).
 177 Beneath the reverse niche on the second row of the Tian Qing stele (519) is an “altar guard Wang Shishi 王市世.” See Beichao Fo Dao, p. 64.
 178 On the area to the right of the obverse niche on the Zhang Qiandu stele (519) is a “director of the altar guard Liu [. . .] 劉□特.” See Bei Wei Guanzhong, p. 131.
 179 This title appears on a stele dated between 508–34 now housed in Xi’an’s Forest of Stelae museum. See Bei Wei Guanzhong, p. 149.”]

GESTERKAMP Lennert
 °2011 [[pdf](#)]

The Heavenly Court. Daoist Temple Painting in China, 1200-1400.
 (Sinica Leidensia; Vol. 96)

Leiden; Boston: Brill.

[xxiii+380p.+36 col. pl.+ 65 figs.+ 4 drawings+1 foldout, bibliography, index.
 ISBN 978-90-04-18490-9.] <<https://doi.org/10.1163/ej.9789004184909.i-470>>

[66: “A similar reference to this type of *chao*-audience ritual is witnessed in the donor scenes on odd mixtures of Buddhist-Daoist steles from the late fifth and early sixth century in southern Shanxi province. For example the Feng Shenyu 馮神育 stele from Lintong 臨潼 and dated to 505 has a donor scene of figures not depicted in one linear horizontal file relegated to the bottom of the composition, as we are used to see from other representations, but in two vertical rows which occupy more than half of the lower part of the stele, the upper part occupied by a seated Buddha in front and a Daoist deity (a Heavenly Worthy) as identified by the fly-whisk held in his hand on its reverse side.¹⁴⁰”

¹⁴⁰ For the Feng Shenyu stele, see Abe, *Ordinary Images*, pp. 274-281 and Shaanxi sheng kaogu yanjiu suo, *Beichao fodaao zaoxiangbei xuanji*, pp. 50-57.]

ZHANG Yan 張燕 (main ed. *bian zhu* 編著); SHAANXISHENG KAOGU YANJIUYUAN 陝西省考古研究院, SHAANXISHENG TONGCHUAN SHI YAOWANGSHAN GUANLIJU 陝西省銅川市藥王山管理局 (*bian* 編)

2013

Shaanxi Yaowangshan beike yishu congji 陝西藥王山碑刻藝術總集
 (*quan ba ce* 全 8 冊)

Shanghai: Shanghai cishu chubanshe 上海辭書出版社.

[8 vols., 2348p.; ISBN 9787532638840.]

book notice:

<<https://www.chugoku-shoten.com/mokuji/cmokuji/72231/72231.pdf>>

[• 7.1 Feng Shenyu dao jiao zaoxiang bei 第七卷 陝西臨潼、渭南地區造像碑, 陝西臨潼、渭南地區造像碑 (二十九通), 一 馮神育道教造像碑 北魏正始二年 (505 年), 附錄 馮萇壽道教造像碑.]

Schwartz Cut, detail of front side, November 30, 1987

• Daniel SCHWARTZ © Frame 18, NegArch ID: PRC87/2-373.18.

Shaanxi province 陝西, Lintong Museum 臨潼博物館, November 30, 1987: *Feng Shenyu deng erbainian ren zaoxiang bei* 馮神育等二百廿人造像碑 (detail, lower part of front)

道民馮今保	邑子馮思善	邑子馮神縱	邑子馮大善
邑子趙林桀	邑子馮神緯	邑子馮道興	
邑子馮作龍	邑子馮文歡	邑子馮世欽	邑子馮龍引
門師張明玉	邑子馮道豐	邑子馮林坊	邑子馮真符
邑師馮洪標	邑子馮道欽	邑子馮神育	邑子馮道多
邑子馮道初	邑子馮道欽	邑子馮洪哲	邑子馮神護
邑子馮洪辨	邑子馮神智	邑子馮神慧	邑子馮天勗
道民祁孟孫	邑子馮伯引	邑子馮道愜	邑子馮文好
	道士李		

front side, lower part, detail:
underlined Chinese characters seen in Schwartz' detail

Rubbings

142×67 cm (碑陽 front)

<https://digiarch.sinica.edu.tw/ImageCache/ImageCache/00/0f/e5/41.jpg>

題名：馮神育二百廿人等造像碑

著錄：《中央研究院歷史語言研究所北魏紀年佛教石刻拓本目錄》28

傳圖登錄號：12795-3

原刻年代：北魏正始二年, 505 CE

原刻地點 / 出土地: 陝西臨潼
釋文: 法師劉洪安□馮道□錄生馮光 [More...](#)
<https://ndweb.iis.sinica.edu.tw/rub_public/System/Buddhist/Detail.jsp?index=0&rubbing_id=9841>
原刻收藏地: 陝西臨潼; 陝西臨潼博物館
造像內容: 道像
墨拓尺寸: 142×67 cm(碑陽)

主要題名: 馮神育二百廿人等造像碑
其他題名: 馮神育等造像記
其他題名: 馮神育等二百廿人造像碑
其他題名: 正始二年造像碑
其他題名: 馮神育二百廿人等造像記
其他題名: 邑子馮神等二百廿人造像

Identifier 登錄號: 12795-3
Type 類型: 佛教、碑誌
Coverage 出土地點現代地名: 陝西, 臨潼
收藏機構現存地點: 陝西臨潼, 陝西臨潼博物館
現藏單位: 中央研究院傅斯年圖書館 Fu Sinian Library, Academia Sinica
Description 叢拓子項: SR2328
Source: 史語所數位資源整合檢索目錄
<https://digiarch.sinica.edu.tw/digiarch_en/content/repository/resource_content.jsp?oid=1834618>

• ABE 2001: 15-15 (figs. 24-25)

FIG. 24.
Rubbing of stele dedicated by Feng Shenyu et al., front, dated to 505, Yaowangshan Museum, Yaoxian (from Zhang Yan and Zhao Chao, Beichao fodao, 50).

FIG. 25.
Rubbing of stele dedicated by Feng Shenyu et al., rear, dated to 505, Yaowangshan Museum, Yaoxian (from Zhang Yan and Zhao Chao, Beichao fodao, 51).

图二 正始二年造像碑拓片（正面）

图三 正始二年造像碑拓片（侧面之一）

图四 正始二年造像碑拓片(碑阴局部)

图五 正始二年造像碑拓片(侧面之二)

CBETA Feng Shenyu Stele Text Transcript

北朝佛教石刻拓片百品 第01冊

No. 11 馮神育等二百廿人造像碑 (1 卷)

【顏娟英主編】

第 1 卷

http://tripitaka.cbeta.org/mobile/index.php?index=I01n0011_001

No. 11

馮神育等二百廿人造像碑

之一 碑陽

法師劉洪安 □馮道□ 錄生馮光□
三洞法師王平定 渥陽縣 傅永洛造 馮道勝 錄生馮伯端
三洞法師牛重蔭 三洞法 師郝□孫 馮道□ 錄生馮同成
錄生真□ 道民馮世紹施 地立壇 息馮道度

馮神苻

錄生馮永興 □□道士洛 高生 錄生馮世安 錄生馮洪族 錄生馮洪莢
錄生馮樹玉 □□馮道秀 錄生馮道起 錄生馮洪虬 錄生馮道養
錄生馮神安 錄□馮□凡 錄生馮道鳳 錄生馮洪明 錄生馮神養

道民馮今保

邑子馮思善 邑子馮神縱 邑子馮大善
邑子趙林桀
邑子祁令標 邑子馮神緯 邑子馮道興
邑子馮仵龍
邑子馮文歡 邑子馮世欽 邑子馮龍引
門師張明玉
邑子馮道豐 邑子趙林坊 邑子馮真苻
邑子祁令宋 邑子馮神育 邑子馮道多
邑師馮洪標
邑子馮道欽 邑子馮洪哲 邑子馮神護
邑子馮道初
邑子祁令智 邑子馮神憇 邑子馮天勗
邑子馮洪辨
邑子馮伯引 邑子馮道禧 邑子馮文好
道民祁孟孫 道士李□

之二 碑陰

李貴姬 袁醜女 尹思香 袁照姬 藺英武 馮標姬
馮巍姬 楊三姬 辛勝姜 李公主 劉要勝 楊銀姜

張白鳳	焦潤姜	劉男香	趙苟女	梁慈姜	馮蠻螭
楊樂姬	王洪姬	王阿正	李女多	柏桃姬	王阿水
邑子楊鳳姬	楊阿俄	王好姬	趙阿女	張叔姬	姜作男
邑子王清姜	尹醜女	楊今英	楊金光	郭伯媚	柏桃花
楊雙媚	孫道姜	郭神女	趙青女	馮華姿	趙桃迎
柏醜姬	趙妙姬	袁女賜	李巧女	劉阿光	劉白佛
	張武媚	趙林姬	王阿迴	牛令姜	董三女
劉文姬					
李阿解	祁男引	蕭勝光	趙阿勝	趙女王	段道女

之三 碑側

□□馮□

道民馮元賜

道民馮周道士馮盛 道士馮還盛息馮神覆

道民馮□德 道民□神□

□民趙道生	錄生張道生	邑子馮道太	邑子馮思政	邑子馮黑退	邑子馮買德
邑子馮世起	邑子馮道明	邑子馮神貴	邑子馮神哲	邑子馮子興	邑子馮顯保
邑子馮伯疆	邑子馮世慶	邑子馮興宋	邑子馮神生	邑子馮市買	邑子趙皇頭
邑子馮道扶	邑子祁伯胡	邑子馮世標	邑子馮文尚	邑子馮市虎	邑子馮始隆
邑子馮道蓋	邑子馮□□	□子馮洛周	邑子馮儀世	邑子馮道穆	邑子馮世豪妻王化

之四 碑側

錄生楊洪超 錄生郭□□

錄生楊洪標 清信士馮□□

邑子柏丞公邑子柏安和邑子柏安起邑□□□□□□祁阿小邑子趙淮業

邑子馮安郡邑子柏惟慶邑子張迴生邑□□□□□子祁市生邑子張道隆 馮連苻

馮連光

夫幽宗玄寂。真麗潛暉。然隱顯沖機。而名隨化浪。洪闡彌廓。遐瓊超倫。雖含養群生。妙容

難尋。自非鏤像汙形。其孰能觀之者哉。大代正始二年秋九月己巳朔廿六日甲午。真

□

道民馮神育同邑二百人等。投委壇靜。仰追冥果。造立石像。永式歸虔。願帝主熙

隆。百□

恭肅。祚延無窮。尊師崇業。諸邑七世以來。生緣眷屬住居。常樂恒在。願々從心。常与善緣。

大道□□。普同慈覆。願〃從心。合邑二百廿人造石像一區。弟立名字。若有人刊試者。身入地獄。

邑□□□海邑子馮道宜邑子馮道集邑子馮黑退邑子馮超宗邑子祁次孫道民馮
弘威

【經文資訊】北朝佛教石刻拓片百品第 01 冊 No. 0011 馮神育等二百廿人造像碑

【版本記錄】CBETA 電子佛典 2016.06，完成日期：2016/06/15

【編輯說明】本資料庫由中華電子佛典協會（CBETA）依北朝佛教石刻拓片百品所編輯

【原始資料】中央研究院歷史語言研究所

【其他事項】本資料庫可自由免費流通，詳細內容請參閱

【[中華電子佛典協會資料庫版權宣告](#)】